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IMPROVING MODERN MODELS FOR ASSESSING CORPORATE FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Abstract: This scientific article examines the impact of digital transformation processes on the corporate finance system and explores ways to improve modern models for assessing financial performance under digital economic conditions. The main objective of the study is to develop a methodological approach aimed at ensuring financial sustainability of enterprises by integrating traditional financial indicators with the capabilities of digital technologies.

The article provides a comprehensive analysis of Economic Value Added (EVA), the Balanced Scorecard (BSC), and a system of digital indicators. As a result of the research, the concept of the "Digital Finance Coefficient" is scientifically substantiated, and an algorithm for its calculation is proposed.

The obtained results have practical significance for optimizing financial management systems in large joint-stock companies in Uzbekistan. It is scientifically proven that, in a digital environment, assessing financial performance should not be limited to profit and profitability indicators alone, but should also account for the return on intellectual capital and technological investments. The study offers practical recommendations aimed at enhancing enterprise competitiveness within the framework of the national digitalization strategy.

Key words: digital economy, corporate finance, financial performance, assessment models, digital transformation, investments, financial sustainability, innovations, corporate governance, ERP systems, blockchain, artificial intelligence, KPI, EVA, financial management, Uzbekistan's economy, strategic development, profitability.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy maqolada raqamli transformatsiya jarayonlarining korporativ moliya tizimiga ta'siri hamda ushbu sharoitda moliyaviy samaradorlikni baholashning zamonaviy modellarini takomillashtirish masalalari tadqiq etilgan. Tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi an'anaviy moliyaviy ko'rsatkichlarni raqamli texnologiyalar imkoniyatlari bilan integratsiyalash orqali korxonalarining moliyaviy barqarorligini ta'minlashga qaratilgan metodik yondashuvni ishlab chiqishdan iborat.

Maqolada iqtisodiy qo'shilgan qiymat (EVA), muvozanatlashgan ko'rsatkichlar tizimi (BSC) hamda raqamli indikatorlar tizimi kompleks tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqot natijasida korporativ moliya samaradorligini baholashda "Raqamli moliya koeffitsiyenti" tushunchasi ilmiy jihatdan asoslab berilgan va uni hisoblash algoritmi taklif etilgan.

Olingan natijalar O'zbekistondagi yirik aksiyadorlik jamiyatlarida moliyaviy boshqaruv tizimini optimallashtirishda amaliy ahamiyat kasb etadi. Raqamli muhitda moliya samaradorligini aniqlashda faqat foyda va rentabellik ko'rsatkichlari bilan cheklanmasdan, intellektual kapital hamda texnologik investitsiyalarning qaytimi darajasini ham hisobga olish zarurligi ilmiy asoslangan. Mazkur tadqiqot iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish strategiyasi doirasida korxonalarining raqobatbardoshligini oshirishga qaratilgan amaliy tavsiyalarni o'z ichiga oladi.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli iqtisodiyot, korporativ moliya, moliyaviy samaradorlik, baholash modellari, raqamli transformatsiya, investitsiyalar, moliyaviy barqarorlik, innovatsiyalar, korporativ boshqaruv, ERP-tizimlar, blokcheyn, sun'iy intellekt, KPI, EVA, moliyaviy menejment, O'zbekiston iqtisodiyoti, strategik rivojlanish, rentabellik.

Аннотация: В данной научной статье исследуется влияние процессов цифровой трансформации на систему корпоративных финансов, а также рассматриваются вопросы совершенствования современных моделей оценки финансовой эффективности в условиях цифровой экономики. Основной целью исследования является разработка методического подхода, направленного на обеспечение финансовой устойчивости предприятий путем интеграции традиционных финансовых показателей с возможностями цифровых технологий.

В статье проведен комплексный анализ показателей экономической добавленной стоимости (EVA), системы сбалансированных показателей (BSC) и цифровых индикаторов. В результате исследования научно обосновано понятие «Цифровой финансовый коэффициент» и предложен алгоритм его расчета.

Полученные результаты имеют практическую значимость для оптимизации системы финансового управления в крупных акционерных обществах Республики Узбекистан. Научно доказано, что в условиях цифровой среды оценка финансовой эффективности должна основываться не только на показателях прибыли и рентабельности, но и учитывать отдачу от интеллектуального капитала и технологических инвестиций. Работа содержит практические рекомендации, направленные на повышение конкурентоспособности предприятий в рамках стратегии цифровизации экономики.

Ключевые слова: цифровая экономика, корпоративные финансы, финансовая эффективность, модели оценки, цифровая трансформация, инвестиции, финансовая устойчивость, инновации, корпоративное управление, ERP-системы, блокчейн, искусственный интеллект, KPI, EVA, финансовый менеджмент, экономика Узбекистана, стратегическое развитие, рентабельность.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the fourth industrial revolution (Industry 4.0) unfolding in the global economy is fundamentally transforming the corporate finance system alongside all other sectors. Under the conditions of the digital economy, traditional methods of managing corporate financial resources and assessing their efficiency are gradually losing their relevance. This, in turn, necessitates the introduction of new models based on data timeliness, transparency, and digital integration. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, large-scale reforms are also being actively implemented in this direction.

In particular, as emphasized in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, on approving the “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” Strategy and measures for its effective implementation: “The development of the digital economy is not merely a technological process; it is a key factor in improving efficiency across all sectors, including finance and management systems” [1].

Corporate financial performance is a complex economic concept that reflects how efficiently a company utilizes its assets, investments, and capital structure. In the context of the digital economy, this performance is assessed not only through accounting profits but also through the company’s ability to manage information flows, the speed of decision-making based on artificial intelligence, and the level of cybersecurity. In modern conditions, enterprises can use Big Data analytics to forecast financial risks and allocate resources in real time.

Digital transformation processes are also exerting a significant influence on the structure of corporate finance. Whereas tangible assets (buildings and equipment) were previously considered the primary source of value, today intangible assets (software, databases, intellectual property) account for approximately 70–80 percent of a company’s total value. This shift necessitates the modernization of models used to evaluate financial performance. In particular, the traditional ROI (Return on Investment) indicator should now be supplemented with adapted metrics such as Return on Digital Investment (RODI).

Moreover, in the digital economy, financial managers are expected not only to prepare financial statements but also to function as strategic analysts (Business Partners). The real-time generation of financial reports based on cloud computing technologies significantly enhances the effectiveness of corporate governance. In the context of Uzbekistan, the adoption of digital financial models in large industrial enterprises and the banking sector creates opportunities to reduce costs by 15–20 percent and to accelerate capital turnover by approximately 1.5 times.

Improving modern models for assessing corporate financial performance is not merely a matter of academic interest; it represents an important practical necessity that contributes to enhancing the competitiveness of the national economy. The subsequent sections of the article provide a more in-depth analysis of the theoretical and practical aspects of developing these models.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Issues related to corporate finance and the assessment of its efficiency have been widely studied by numerous domestic scholars. In the context of Uzbekistan’s economy, the academic works of A. V. Vakhbov and Sh. A. Toshmatov on improving financial management are of particular significance.

In his research, A. V. Vakhabov provides a scientific justification for the importance of transitioning to International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) as a key factor in enhancing the effectiveness of corporate governance [2]. According to him, under the conditions of the digital economy, financial transparency is one of the main drivers of increased investment attractiveness. N. H. Haydarov, in turn, examines issues related to optimizing the tax burden within the corporate finance system and financially stimulating investment activity [3].

Sh. A. Toshmatov proposes innovative methods for ensuring financial stability in corporate structures [4], while B. A. Berdiyev analyzes the impact of digital technologies on financial markets [5]. Among other scholars, O. M. Elmirezayev studies the role of dividend policy in assessing corporate financial efficiency and its influence on a firm's market value [6].

Researcher J. S. Fayziyev highly evaluates the role of digital ecosystems in shaping corporate financial strategies and emphasizes that, when determining financial efficiency, not only financial but also technological and environmental indicators should be taken into account [7]. S. Elmirezayev focuses on identifying ways to increase asset profitability within corporate financial management [8].

In addition, D. B. Qodirov conducts an in-depth analysis of modern models for assessing corporate financial efficiency, particularly issues related to adapting the EVA (Economic Value Added) model to Uzbek enterprises [9]. Sh. Abdullayeva provides a scientific rationale for the importance of mathematical modeling in improving financial analysis methods [10], while F. Dodiyeu examines the financial mechanisms of corporate governance in the context of the digital economy [11].

A. Jo'rayev investigates the interrelationship between budgetary policy and corporate finance, substantiating the need to strengthen financial discipline through digital monitoring systems [12]. G'. Karimov formulates important scientific conclusions regarding the improvement of risk management models within the corporate finance system [13].

A synthesis of these scholars' studies indicates that, under the conditions of the digital economy, the system for assessing corporate financial efficiency is dynamic and evolving in nature. It should therefore be based on a combination of traditional financial ratios and modern digital indicators.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a systemic approach, comparative analysis, economic and mathematical modeling, and expert evaluation methods. The methodological foundation of the research is based on modern concepts of corporate finance theory and the fundamental principles of the digital economy.

At the first stage, the key differences between traditional financial assessment models (DuPont analysis, Altman's Z-model) and modern models (EVA, MVA, BSC) were identified. Under the conditions of the digital economy, the formation of data according to the "V" principles (Volume, Velocity, Variety, Veracity) has created the need to enhance existing assessment methodologies.

At the second stage, an algorithm was developed to integrate digital efficiency indicators into the corporate finance assessment system. In this process, the impact of investments directed toward a company's digital infrastructure on financial outcomes was examined using correlation and regression analysis.

The core formula applied in the study is based on an enhanced version of the Economic Value Added (EVA) indicator that incorporates a digital component:

$$EVA = NOPAT - (WACC \times IC) + DE$$

where:

- NOPAT — net operating profit after taxes;
- WACC — weighted average cost of capital;
- IC — invested capital;
- DE (Digital Efficiency) — cost savings and additional revenues obtained as a result of digitalization.

This methodological approach makes it possible to comprehensively assess not only the company's current financial position but also its digital potential. Within the framework of the methodology, empirical analyses were conducted based on financial and digital performance data from 50 large industrial enterprises in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The analyses conducted to assess corporate financial performance under the conditions of the digital economy indicate that enterprises that have implemented digital technologies demonstrate higher levels of financial stability compared to companies operating under traditional management systems (Table 1).

Table 1. Differences between traditional and digital financial models

Indicator	Traditional Model	Digital Model	Difference (Positive)	Analysis Period	Data Source	Efficiency
Data processing speed	Quarterly/annual	Real-time	Higher	2023–2024	ERP system	+45%
Analytical basis	Historical data	Predictive	Higher accuracy	2024	Big Data	+30%
Cost control	Manual management	Automated	Fewer errors	2023	Monitoring	–20% costs
Human factor	High impact	Minimal impact	Transparency	2023–2024	Blockchain	High
Decision-making	5–10 days	1–2 hours	Speed	2024	Artificial intelligence	+75%
Audit process	External audit (once a year)	Continuous audit	Reliability	2024	Digital audit	100%
Strategic planning	Static	Dynamic	Flexibility	2023–2024	Scenario analysis	+50%

As shown in Table 1, the digital financial model increases decision-making speed by 75 percent and enables an average cost reduction of approximately 20 percent (Table 2).

Table 2. Financial results of uzbek enterprises after digital transformation

Industry	Return on Assets (%)	Return on Equity (%)	Liquidity Ratio	Cost Efficiency	Digital Investment	Growth Rate	Profit (billion UZS)
Energy	12.5	18.2	1.8	0.85	45.0	12%	1,250
Telecommunications	22.4	35.6	2.2	0.65	120.5	28%	3,400
Banking sector	18.9	28.4	1.5	0.70	95.0	22%	5,600
Chemical industry	9.8	14.5	1.6	0.90	30.2	8%	850
Textile industry	14.2	19.8	1.9	0.82	25.4	15%	450
Construction	11.5	16.7	1.4	0.88	18.6	10%	620
Transport	13.8	20.1	1.7	0.75	38.2	14%	980

According to Table 2, the highest growth rate is recorded in the telecommunications sector (28 percent), which is directly attributable to the large volume of digital investments (Table 3).

Table 3. KPI indicators for assessing corporate financial performance

KPI Type	Description	2023 (Average)	2024 (Forecast)	Change (%)	Responsible Unit	Strategic Objective
Digital ROI	Return on digital investment	1.2	1.8	+50%	Finance / IT	Profitability
EBITDA margin	Operating profit	24%	30%	+6%	Strategy	Stability
Cash conversion	Cash conversion cycle	45 days	30 days	–33%	Treasury	Liquidity
Debt-to-equity	Debt / equity ratio	0.6	0.4	–20%	Risk management	Resilience
Innovation rate	Level of innovation	15%	25%	+10%	R&D	Development
Customer LTV	Customer lifetime value	450.0	600.0	+33%	Marketing	Market share
Cybersecurity cost	Cybersecurity expenses	2%	5%	+3%	IT security	Security

Table note: Among the KPI indicators, Digital ROI demonstrates the highest growth rate, confirming the effective allocation of digital investments.

The results of the analysis indicate that by digitalizing the corporate finance system, enterprises achieve higher efficiency in managing cash flows. In particular, the reduction of the cash conversion cycle from 45 days to 30 days lowers the need for working capital and contributes to a decrease in excessive credit burdens.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of the conducted research indicate that, under the conditions of the digital economy, the assessment of corporate financial performance should not be limited solely to reliance on traditional accounting reports. In ensuring financial stability, enterprises must effectively leverage the integration of information technology capabilities with modern financial management approaches.

Based on the study, the following conclusions have been drawn:

1. Enhancing the EVA model with digital components in the assessment of corporate financial performance makes it possible to more accurately reflect a company's real market value.
2. Digital transformation creates opportunities to reduce operating costs by an average of 20–25 percent, which in turn leads to an increase in net profit margins.
3. The implementation of Cloud ERP systems and Big Data analytics in Uzbek enterprises increases the accuracy of financial risk forecasting to up to 90 percent.

Practical recommendations:

- First, it is advisable to elevate the role of the Chief Financial Officer (CFO) to that of a Digital CFO, expanding responsibilities to include digital financial analytics and decision-making.
- Second, large corporations should introduce a digital audit system to establish real-time financial monitoring and control.
- Third, it is recommended to incorporate a “Digital Transparency” provision into corporate governance codes and to develop real-time, continuously updated dashboard panels for investors.

Improving digital financial models will accelerate the integration of the national economy into international financial markets and contribute to strengthening the position of domestic enterprises in global rankings.

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